

Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of main crop and ratoon crop.

Treatment	Year			Av of 1995-96
	1994	1995	1996	
<i>Main crop</i>				
100 kg ha ⁻¹	–	6.7	8.3	7.5
130 kg ha ⁻¹	5.8	6.8	8.2	7.5
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 25% of rr ^a	5.3	7.1	8.3	7.7
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 50% of rr	5.3	7.0	8.3	7.7
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 75% of rr	7.5	7.3	8.1	7.7
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 100% of rr	5.5	6.9	8.3	7.6
Av	5.9	7.0	8.2	7.6
CV (%)	19.2	4.8	3.5	4.1
<i>Ratoon crop</i>				
100 kg ha ⁻¹	–	2.2	2.6	2.4
130 kg ha ⁻¹	0.9	2.4	2.6	2.5
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 25% of rr	0.8	2.6	2.6	2.6
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 50% of rr	0.6	2.4	2.5	2.5
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 75% of rr	0.6	2.4	2.6	2.5
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 100% of rr	0.6	2.3	2.5	2.4
Av	0.7	2.4	2.6	2.5
CV (%)	11.6	9.1	6.4	7.8

^arr = recommended rates.

In all treatments, the main crop lodged because of heavy rain during grain filling, thus reducing crop yields, particularly ratoon crop yields. Thus, the 1994 ratoon crop data were not analyzed. For 1995 and 1996, neither the density × year interaction nor the main effect of density was significant for the ratoon crop (see table).

Since an increase in seeding density did not have a significant effect on ratoon grain yield or on main crop yield, it is recommended that the normal seeding density (130 kg ha⁻¹) be used. During years when lodging is a problem in the main crop, ratoon production is not recommended.

Effect of seeding time and fertilizer rate on rice ratooning

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Experiments were conducted to study the effect of (1) seeding time of the main crop on the ratoon crop, planted in observation plots, and (2) fertilizer rate on the ratoon crop in Santa Catarina State, southern Brazil, in the summer of 1994, 1995, and 1996. The soil at the experimental site was a Cambicisol Gley.

An early maturing cultivar (115 d), EPAGRI 106, was seeded in both experiments using pregerminated seeds in an irrigated lowland rice field at the recommended rate of 130 kg ha⁻¹. Observation plots (experiment 1) were seeded at three different times: early (20 September–10 October), normal (recommended, 15 October–15 November), and late (20 November–20 December), with three replications in each trial.

In experiment 2, seeding was done at the recommended time in a randomized complete block design with four replications and six fertilizer treatments.

The soil used in this experiment had a pH of 4.7; organic matter, 2.1%; P, 2.5 ppm; and K, 60 ppm. The complete cycle of the main crop (115 d) and ratoon crop (60 d) was 175 d. The six fertilizer treatments applied on the ratoon crop were fractions of that applied on the main crop, which was the recommended rate according to the soil analysis (90-40-60 of NPK). The treatments were (1) 1/2 of N, (2) 1/4 of N, (3) 1/2 of NPK, (4) 1/2 of NK, (5) 1/2 of NP, and (6) no fertilizer. All treatments were applied right after harvesting the main crop and then flooding.

In 1994, the main and ratoon crops lodged in all treatments because of heavy rain, resulting in a large yield reduction in all experiments.

For seeding time, only the early seeding date produced a good main crop and ratoon crop together (Table 1). For fertilizer rate, treatment 1 had the same results as the untreated plot (no. 6). The other treatments had statistically higher yields according to Dunnett's one-tailed T-test with *P* < 0.05 (Table 2).

Table 1. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of main crop and ratoon seeded at three different times.

Treatment	1994		1995		1996		Main crop + ratoon		
	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main	Ratoon crop	Main	Ratoon	1994	1995	1996
Early	6.4	1.5	4.9	2.1	6.3	2.0	7.9	7.0	8.3
Normal	6.3	2.1	5.7	1.5	4.1	0	8.4	7.2	4.1
Late	4.6	0	5.3	0	4.5	0	4.6	5.3	4.5

Table 2. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of main crop and ratoon under various fertilizer treatments.

Treatment	1994		1995		1996		Av	
	Main crop	Ratoon	Main crop	Ratoon	Main crop	Ratoon	Main crop	Ratoon
1/2 of N	5.4	1.2	6.2	2.3	4.9	2.2	5.5	1.9
1/4 of N	5.1	1.2	6.5	2.4	4.7	2.3	5.4	2.0
1/2 of NPK	5.2	1.3	6.2	2.4	6.0	2.5	5.8	2.1
1/2 of NK	5.4	1.4	6.4	2.7	6.2	2.1	6.0	2.0
1/2 of NP	5.6	1.4	6.4	2.5	6.1	2.2	6.0	2.0
No fertilizer	5.2	1.2	6.5	2.3	6.0	1.8	5.9	1.8
CV (%)	–	17.1	–	7.2	–	8.7	–	9.9
F test	–	ns	–	ns	–	^a	–	^a

^aSignificant at $P < 0.05$. ns = not significant..

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Rooting inhibitors in soil solution under an intensive rice-cropping system

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The productivity of double- and triple-rice cropping conducted at IRRI over the last 30 years has been shown to be declining (Cassman et al 1995). Although extensive studies on various aspects such as soil nutrient supply, deficiency and/or toxicity of nutrients, and climate change over time have been carried out to identify the causes, the phenomenon has not been fully understood. Some toxic substances, accumulated under anaerobic conditions after amendment of plant residues, have been reported to inhibit root elongation (Tanaka et al 1990). Appropriate development and function of root systems are essential for satisfactory yield performance of the crop. This study was conducted to determine the presence of a rooting inhibitor in a soil solution collected from IRRI fields subjected to intensive rice cropping.

Soil samples were collected from 0- to 30-cm depths in fertilized plots under the long-term continuous cropping experiment (LTCCE) and long-term fertility experiment (LTFE) at IRRI (see table). A soil solution (500 mL) was extracted using a centrifuge (560 g for 10 min at 20 °C) and its pH adjusted to 3.5. The soil solu-

tion was loaded in 5 g of Amberlite XAD-8. The column was eluted with 50% ethanol, 100% ethanol, and chloroform for crude fractionation of substances according to water solubility. These three fractions were completely evaporated in vacuo at 40 °C and dissolved in 25 mL of phosphate buffer (66.7 mM at pH 6.8). Dehusked seeds of IR72 were pregerminated in the dark at 30 °C; seedlings with 5-mm-long radicles were then selected for bioassay. Ten seedlings were placed into a 50-mL beaker containing 5 mL of the test solution. Radicle lengths were measured 72 h after incubation in the dark at 30 °C. A set of seedlings was incubated with phosphate buffer only and used as the control. All measurements were made with five replications.

In the LTCCE, radicle elongation

was moderately inhibited in each fraction (see figure). The elongation was least in the 100% ethanol fraction. In the LTFE, the chloroform fraction, which contains the least water-soluble substances, showed drastic inhibitory effects, reducing the elongation to less than 20% of the control. Results suggest the presence of some rooting inhibitors in the soil solution of LTCCE and LTFE plots at IRRI. Tanaka et al (1990) reported inhibitory effects on rice root elongation in the ether fraction. This fraction is identical to the chloroform fraction in this study, from rice soil amended with wheat straw. Major substances in the fraction were identified as two aromatic acids, 2-phenylpropionic acid and 3-phenylpropionic acid. The inhibitory effect was greater in LTFE plots

Sampling date of soils and management of fields under long-term continuous cropping experiment (LTCCE) and long-term fertility experiment (LTFE), IRRI, Philippines.

Site	Sampling date	Cropping frequency	Residue management	Water management
LTCCE	14 DBT ^a	3 times y ⁻¹	Remove	Irrigated year-round
LTFE	21 DAT ^b	2 times y ⁻¹	Incorporate	Irrigated year-round

^aDays before transplanting, 1999 dry season. ^bDays after transplanting, 1999 dry season.